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ECONOMIC GROWTH AND NATIONAL SECURITY IN THE CONTEXT OF NATURAL RESOURCE POTENTIAL MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT: The study aims to conceptualise a model for managing natural resource potential that fosters both sustainable economic development and national security, using Ukraine as a primary case study. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the paper integrates national and international data on GDP, extraction and consumption of natural resources, resource rents, and security threat indices. Correlation analysis was conducted across 22 countries, alongside an in-depth examination of Ukraine's energy and mineral resource dynamics from 2017 to 2023. The study identifies a strong positive relationship between economic growth and the share of resource rent in GDP across most countries, while also revealing Ukraine's inefficient use of coal and energy resources, and a shifting correlation between security threats and economic performance pre- and post-war. Based on these findings, a conceptual model is proposed that emphasises the need for program-targeted and project-based governance, resource capitalisation, and institutional reform to enhance resilience and economic sovereignty.

KEYWORDS: global resource management index, global security threat index; management structures, natural resource assets, resource rent

Introduction

Despite significant business successes in ensuring resource and product supplies on a global scale, the increasing geo-economic threats in the 21st century, associated not only with the strain on resource bases but also with trade wars, military-political conflicts, have led to the reevaluation of the factor of national security and its dialectical interrelation with economic growth and resource management. The problem became particularly acute due to the impact of the Russian Federation's war against Ukraine on global trade and supply chains in strategic sectors such as energy and agriculture.

Against the backdrop of intensified globalisation over the past decades, the interrelation between economic growth, the effectiveness of managing natural resource potential, and national security has become increasingly strengthened. Achieving an optimal state of the economy cannot be pursued at the expense of disrupting external economic activities that correspond to national interests. On the one hand, this creates significant potential for national economies to unfold new opportunities and competitive advantages. On the other hand, it exacerbates potential threats to national security and increases the sensitivity of economies to the turbulent conditions of contemporary geopolitics. In the context of the interrelation between national security, economic growth, and resource management, the relevance of the economic dimension of national security is heightened. This includes the level of development of critical sectors of the economy, such as the defence industry, IT, metallurgy, agro-industrial complex, energy, pharmaceuticals, and others.

The relationship between national security and the economic sphere is characterised by close correlations and loops of direct and reverse connections. National security is understood here as ensuring the protection of critical infrastructure, sectors, and processes that are crucial for the sustainable functioning and growth of the economy in the conditions of the modern geo-economic environment. At the same time, for each country, depending on the specificity of its development, natural resource potential, and institutional conditions, there are contextual factors unique to it. These contextual factors include the size of critical sectors, the level of state ownership, the degree of development of public-private partnerships, specialization in the international division of labor, dependence on imported raw materials to meet energy, food, and resource needs, the depth of integration into regional and global structures, the share of foreign ownership in critical sectors, adequacy or deficiency of digital skills, scientific-technological developments, and innovations in critical sectors. These contextual factors, depending on how effectively they are managed, either form competitive advantages and foundations for sustainable economic growth or pose risks to national security (Retter et al., 2020).

In the turbulent geo-economic environment, the opportunities for economies to grow and strengthen national security depend on balanced development of critical sectors of the economy through effective utilisation of available natural resource potential (Shultz et al., 2020) and proper institutional support (Khundadze, 2024). The ability of the economy to reproduce its natural resource potential and reduce dependence on resource imports for uninterrupted satisfaction of internal markets with energy, raw materials, food, information, and technological resources creates the potential for economic development and strengthens national security. However, even in conditions of economic stability, it is challenging to ensure the development of all spheres of national security simultaneously and to the fullest extent, as the latter constitutes a system of protection against political, economic, military, informational, social, environmental, and scientific-technological threats. Only through the comprehensive utilisation of institutional means (legal, administrative, economic, technological, etc.), reducing corruption and inefficiency in the development and management of natural resources, can economic and social progress be achieved (Zhang & Teng, 2023).

According to the Global Threat Index methodology, national security protection should target critical socio-economic risks, including resource conflicts, poor governance, elite fragmentation, recession, social unrest, brain drain, weakened public services, loss of institutional trust, human rights violations, demographic pressures (e.g., refugees), and economic dependence (Global Economy, 2023). An economic downturn deepens amid falling GDP, rising unemployment, inflation, and reduced productivity. Macroeconomic instability also drives down trade revenues, foreign investment, and currency value. Uneven development and socio-economic disparities increase social tension and the risk of extremism (Nabin et al., 2022). Furthermore, brain drain (emigration of skilled workers) can hinder growth, though it may boost productivity through global talent exchange if effec-

tively managed (Yu, 2021). A serious threat to national security is the erosion of state legitimacy and the rule of law, reflected in declining public trust, rising corruption, and elite capture. This can lead to protests, civil unrest, and weakened institutional stability. Related risks include the deterioration of public services, violations of human rights, and misuse of 'national security' narratives to suppress freedoms (Van Vark, 2021; Christakis & Bouslimani, 2021). Demographic pressure is a key national security risk, encompassing stress on essential resources like food, water, and housing, as well as population growth, age imbalances, and displacement due to conflicts or disasters. The influx of refugees may overwhelm state capacities, leading to humanitarian and security challenges (O'Sullivan, 2020; Shultz et al., 2020).

Thus, preserving natural resource potential is increasingly urgent, as poor management undermines sustainable development and national security. There is a growing need to transform national strategies to align economic growth, security, and effective resource use. Exploring the complex links between resource extraction, consumption, rent, governance, and threat levels is thus a vital research direction. In the context of Ukraine's war-driven instability, efficient resource management becomes a strategic national priority.

Therefore, this study aims to conceptualise existing approaches to analysing the relationship between economic growth, national security, and natural resource potential, and to develop a model for its effective management. In order to fulfil the set aim, the following research hypotheses were put forward:

- Hypothesis 1: There is a strong positive correlation between the global economic growth and the extraction of strategically important natural resources, such as oil, coal, and gold.
- Hypothesis 2: National security threats and economic growth are inversely related; as the level of threats increases, economic growth declines.
- Hypothesis 3: In Ukraine, there is an inverse relationship between economic growth and national security threats, meaning that heightened security risks are associated with slower economic growth.

The study is based on three hypotheses, formulated to be thought-provoking and accessible to readers and researchers. These hypotheses were tested using logical and mathematical methods. All three were rejected, as briefly noted in the conclusion and discussed in detail in the results section. These hypotheses were put forward on the basis that the statistical materials to confirm or refute them can be found in the public domain in an up-to-date form, such as the State Statistics Service of Ukraine and other non-governmental sources. Notably, no prior research has simultaneously addressed all three hypotheses, making this study the first to do so.

Literature review

The natural resource potential of a country reflects the sufficiency of its natural resource assets, namely the material assets in the form of space and reserves of natural resources, which serve as the material basis for the country's economic growth and directly influence its national security. The natural resource potential is linked to addressing the challenge of meeting the needs of a growing population, projected to reach 9.7 billion people by 2050 (Van Hoof et al., 2019). In particular, land and resource assets are a factor in economic growth and cyclical fluctuations (Song et al., 2020). While natural resource assets drive development, their utilisation can have negative consequences on security due to environmental degradation (Wang et al., 2022), insufficient capitalisation, and unclear property rights delineation (Fan et al., 2021). The World Trade Organization defines natural resources as "stocks of materials that exist in the natural environment, which are scarce and economically valuable in production or consumption, either in their unprocessed state or after minimal processing" (World Trade Organization, 2010). According to Olanrewaju et al. (2020), natural resources serve as platforms for generating export revenues.

Regions abundant in natural resources, such as energy and minerals, can effectively convert their resource advantages into economic development benefits for a country or region through export trade (Qiang & Jian, 2020). The issue of the relationship between economic development and natural resource endowments is of interest to scholars, particularly in light of the "resource curse" paradox, whereby countries rich in natural resources demonstrate worse economic development indicators

than countries with limited resources (Amiri et al., 2019; Dogan et al., 2020). Indeed, in many countries, the role of natural resources is not a significant factor in economic development, and in some regions, natural resources have a negative impact on their economic growth (Xue, 2024). For instance, regions rich in natural resources, such as Nigeria, Venezuela, and the Netherlands, among others, tend to have worse economic development indicators compared to countries with relatively limited natural resources, such as Switzerland, Japan, South Korea, and others.

The term “resource curse” was first coined by Richard Auty (1993) to analyse the phenomenon where countries rich in natural resources were unable to leverage this wealth for economic development and experienced lower economic growth rates compared to countries with fewer resources. In contemporary research, the paradox has been explained by the high dependence of resource-rich countries on resources and the low diversification of exports in developing countries (Zarach & Parteka, 2023). This is compounded by volatile commodity prices, which negatively impact exports, savings, and investments, leading to macroeconomic instability in resource-exploiting poor countries (Owusu-Antwi et al., 2019). Developed economies with limited natural resources mitigate this through early and intensive specialisation in production sectors (Kuralbayeva & Stefanski, 2013). At the same time, other scholars have argued the paradox by highlighting that a large share of raw materials and low-tech goods in exports negatively impacts economic growth due to the displacement effect on manufacturing industries (the so-called “Dutch disease” effect) (Mien & Goujon, 2022). This is compounded by indirect effects stemming from weak institutional factors in certain countries, leading to heightened corruption (Adomako et al., 2021), ineffective natural resource management, and excessive bureaucracy (Abdulahi et al., 2019).

The consequences of the “resource curse” paradox naturally include low economic growth rates in resource-rich countries (Zagozina, 2014) and a reorientation of macroeconomic policy priorities towards strengthening the financial systems of these countries (Seyfettin et al., 2020). Since in resource-rich countries, the exploitation of natural resources often prioritises the extraction of resources for export rather than domestic production, a problem arises with the contraction of the trade sector. When the financial system is strengthened, the rent from natural resources is transferred to the real sector. With proper control over corruption, transparent resource management, and effective institutionalisation, the transfer of rent from natural resources to the real sector and productive investments contributes to stable and tangible economic growth (Seyfettin et al., 2020).

The issue of the interrelation between natural resource management and national security is not as actively explored in the scientific literature as economic growth; however, the study by Trung suggests that a country’s security significantly improves after reaching a certain threshold level of resources and resource rent. Beyond this level, when countries excessively invest in military security, they inevitably may lose a certain portion of resource rent and, as a result, experience lower rates of economic growth, with the marginal benefit of military expenditure ultimately diminishing. Therefore, countries will reduce their military expenditures as the volume of resource rent increases; that is, a low level of resource rent increases military spending, while a high level reduces it (Trung, 2021).

Compared to other natural resources, oil represents the most significant competitive advantage. Countries possessing it receive significant revenue from its export. The transfer of income from oil exports to the real sector promotes economic growth by stimulating further investments and societal production. Efficient transfer of oil revenues is ensured by a robust financial system and, at the same time, requires a proper level of financial security, positively impacting it (Seyfettin et al., 2020). The strategic function of the financial system lies in transferring savings to the real sector at optimal costs. In resource-rich countries, the transfer of export revenues from natural resources to non-productive sectors of the real economy promotes the expansion of productive investments and, as a result, economic growth (Seyfettin et al., 2020).

Thus, it becomes evident that the lack or inadequacy of natural resources is not the determining factor for economic growth. Instead, institutional factors, including the efficiency of resource management, play a significant role. The effectiveness of natural resource management is determined not only by its rational use and balancing with extraction reserves, the ability to resolve natural resource conflicts, but also by the country’s capacity for reconfiguring and diversifying supply chains to reduce dependence on resources as sources of production. The ability to adapt product supply to multiple sources is precisely what mitigates the consequences that affect national security (Beal, 2022). The process of restructuring and diversifying supply chains can lead to the emergence of diplomatic ten-

sion, as countries attempt to reduce their dependence on geopolitical “adversaries” in critical sectors of the economy. Specifically, this refers to resources such as rare earth minerals used in semiconductors and other high-tech products, in which China holds a competitive advantage. The economies of Japan, the United States, and the United Kingdom are particularly critical and sensitive to these resources (Vekasi, 2021).

In the course of the literature review, methodological limitations were identified in approaches to the three interrelated trends of socio-economic development: economic growth, national security, and natural resource management. In the scientific literature, there is no unified approach to studying the trends of interconnection and interdependence between the use of natural resource potential, economic growth, and national security. Furthermore, a conceptual model for the comprehensive management of natural resource assets to intensify economic growth amidst increasing national security threats has not been developed.

Materials and methods

The methodological framework of the study is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Methodological design of research

Due to the lack of statistical data for all the investigated indicators on a wider range of intervals (5-20 years), our attention was focused on the period 2017-2020. We studied the trends of correlation with economic growth for processes such as energy resource consumption, mineral extraction, and changes in the level of national security threats, and determined the corresponding correlation coefficients.

Ukraine was selected as the primary subject of analysis due to its unique geopolitical and economic context. As a country facing ongoing military aggression and systemic threats to national security, Ukraine combines significant natural resource potential with prolonged economic instability. This combination, alongside recent institutional reforms in property rights, governance, deregulation, and industrial modernisation, makes it a relevant case for evaluating the interrelation between economic growth, national security, and natural resource management in high-risk environments. To complement the case study, data from 22 additional countries were analysed. These countries were selected based on the availability of key indicators and represent a diverse sample across levels of economic development, geographical conditions, and climatic zones. Aggregated data include indicators such as resource extraction (oil, coal, gold), national security threat ratings, quality of resource governance, and economic growth rates, enabling a broader comparative analysis of correlation patterns across contexts.

The research involves the following stages:

- detailing the threats to economic, socio-political, and environmental development and their categorisation into various spheres of national security;

- justification of the impact of the global index of natural resource management quality on economic growth and national security;
- determination of the role of natural resources and their rent in ensuring economic growth;
- aggregation of data on the production capacities of 22 countries worldwide regarding oil, coal, and gold extraction, the index of natural resource management quality, threats to national security, resource rent in GDP structure (static analysis), and its changes during 2020-2023 (dynamic analysis), and identification of correlation coefficients between these parameters and economic growth;
- aggregation of data on the extraction of minerals and consumption of energy resources in Ukraine, dynamics of GDP for the years 2017-2020, and determination of correlation coefficients between them;
- studying the trend of correlation between the level of threats to Ukraine's national security and its economic growth during the pre-war period of 2017-2020 and from 2017 to 2023;
- justification of the conceptual model of effective management of natural resource potential for intensifying economic growth and strengthening national security.

Figure 2 depicts a block diagram illustrating the influence of threats to national security, the quality of government management of natural resources, and resource rent on economic growth.

Figure 2. Spectrum of threats to national security, quality of resource management, resource rent as factors of economic growth

To analyse the impact of national security threats on economic growth, we categorised them into key domains: ecological, social, political, and economic security. Each category was operationalised using relevant indicators from open-access international indexes and databases. Ecological threats were assessed through indicators related to competition over access to natural resources, resource rent, and environmental degradation caused by their mismanagement (Schelens & Diemer, 2021). These threats include tensions arising from unequal distribution and control of resource benefits. Social security risks included demographic pressure, brain drain, and human rights violations. Indicators such as population growth rates, emigration of skilled labour, and remittance flows were considered. Additionally, legal system abuses and social dissatisfaction were used to proxy risks of unrest and public discontent. Political threats were assessed using indices of elite fragmentation and gov-

ernment legitimacy. These reflect the level of institutional cohesion, corruption, trust in government, and the quality of public service provision. Economic security threats encompassed indicators of economic decline, structural inequality, and external interference. Metrics included GDP dynamics, inflation, unemployment, and dependence on foreign aid or investment. This typology formed the basis for integrating security dimensions into the correlation analysis with economic performance.

To assess the quality of natural resource governance and its relation to economic growth and national security, the study uses the Global Natural Resource Management Quality Index developed for OECD member states. This composite indicator integrates socio-political, economic, and technological parameters, allowing for cross-country comparisons and evaluation of institutional capacity in resource management. The methodology is grounded in the assumption that natural resource use affects macroeconomic performance and environmental sustainability. Empirical literature supports the existence of a correlation between natural resource exploitation, rent generation, and GDP growth, particularly in models where minimal environmental costs and high capital accumulation are observed. However, the long-term sustainability of such growth is often undermined by environmental degradation due to deforestation, pollution, and inefficient fossil fuel extraction (Tahir et al., 2022; Shahzad et al., 2022).

These theoretical insights informed the selection of indicators and the structuring of correlation analysis across 22 countries and Ukraine, focusing on fossil fuel production, renewable energy use, and the overall quality of resource management.

Results of the research

Aggregating data on the production capabilities of 22 countries worldwide regarding the extraction of oil, coal, and gold, the index of natural resource management quality, threats to national security, resource rents in GDP structure (static analysis), and its changes during 2020-2023 (dynamic analysis) and identifying correlation coefficients of these parameters with economic growth

Table 1 contains aggregated data on the production resource capabilities of 22 countries worldwide, their indices of national security threats, quality of state management of natural resources, the share of rents in GDP, and economic growth for 2020-2023, reflecting the ratio of GDP volume in 2023 to 2020.

Table 1. Resource production potential, level of security threats, quality of natural resource management, resource rent, and economic growth in some countries of the world

Countries	Coal production 2022	Oil production 2022	Gold production 2020 kg	Security Threats index 2023	Resources Governance index 2021	Natural resources income % in GDP 2021	GDP index % 2023/2020
China	4766784.5	4090.00	365340	4.9	55	1.71	25.2
India	1040500.19	612.82	1757	6.0	702017	3.16	32.6
USA	593608.25	11910.62	193000	4.7	742017	1.28	26.1
Australia	510991.19	310.92	327825	2.1	712017	13.36	28.6
Russia	508541.28	10314.47	305040	8.3	452017	18.51	52.3
South Africa	269291.78	0.95	95883	6.6	572017	7.33	20.5
Germany	144183.25	33.24	0.00	2.3	-	0.08	5.1
Kazakhstan	127438.13	1726.51	62865	4.00	562017	26.84	34.9
Colombia	59883.59	754.27	47830	6.7	76	5.32	28.1
Canada	45352.31	4543.29	169687	2.2	752017	4.95	30.3
Norway	128.97	1704.3	0.00	1.4	862017	10.05	56.8
North Korea	23866.11	0.00	1000	7.4	-	-	10.8

Countries	Coal production 2022	Oil production 2022	Gold production 2020 kg	Security Threats index 2023	Resources Governance index 2021	Natural resources income % in GDP 2021	GDP index % 2023/2020
Brazil	6834.85	3021.51	78000	6.2	712017	7.94	41.2
Iran	1814.4	3293.4	7600	7.00	382017	30.45	74.1
Ukraine	1714.09	6.67	0.00	10.00	492017	7.51	4.5
Japan	750.53	3.24	7590	1.5	-	0.05	-16.5
UK	717.54	744.92	60.00	2.9	772017	0.59	14.8
Swaziland	241.13	0.00	1.00	4.5	-	3.0	23.1
Venezuela	217.16	703.66	480.00	6.7	332017	-	7.4
Argentina	27.21	582.67	58800	4.3	572017	2.65	61.3
UA Emirates	0.00	3467.87	0.00	2.3	422017	17.63	48.2
Qatar	0.00	1321.19	0.00	1.0	432017	27.29	67.4
Correlation coefficient	0.00	0.35	0.0	0.0	0.3	1.0	-

Source: author's work based on Global Economy (2023) and Trading Economics (2025).

Due to the absence of all RGI data for 2021, and data for 2017, this parameter was analyzed in relation to the GDP dynamics indicator for 2016-2019 (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Quality of government management in the oil, gas, and mining sectors and economic growth in various countries worldwide

Source: author's work based on Natural Resource Governance Institute (2021) and Trading Economics (2025).

Figure 4 illustrates the relationship between the index of national security threats and the share of resource rent in GDP.

We aggregated statistical data on the consumption of thermal energy resources, electrical energy resources, renewable resources such as hydroelectric, biofuels, waste, wind, and solar energy, as well as the extraction of gas, oil (with gas condensate), coal, and iron ore. The impact of these resource parameters on the dynamics of GDP in Ukraine for 2017-2020 was studied (Table 2).

Figure 4. Index of national security threats and the share of resource rent in GDP of various countries worldwide
 Source: author's work based on Global Economy (2023).

Table 2. Aggregated data on the extraction of minerals, oil, and gas, consumption of energy resources, and GDP dynamics in Ukraine for 2017-2020

Resource Parameter / GDP	2017	2018	2019	2020	Correlation coefficient with economic growth
Consumption of Thermal Energy Resources (Gcal) / GDP	58927609	60109447	57860176	56501836	-0.7
Consumption of Electrical Energy Resources (thousand kWh) / thsd.kW×h	89568378	90820372	88795195	83888551	-0.7
Consumption of Renewable Energy Resources. thousand tons of oil equivalent (toe)	3907	4303	4335	5687	0.81
Natural Gas Extraction. billion cubic meters	20.5	20.8	20.7	20.2	-0.30
Coal Extraction. million tons	34.9	33.3	31.2	28.8	-0.96
Oil Extraction. million tons	2.45	2.46	2.468	2.47	0.996
Iron Ore Extraction. million tons	60.5	60.3	63.2	78.8	0.74
Gross Domestic Product. trillion UAH	2.98	3.56	3.98	4.22	-

Source: author's work based on the State Statistics Service of Ukraine (2024a) and Statista Research Department (2024).

Figure 5. Gross Domestic Product of Ukraine (trillion UAH) and Security Threat Index (STI) in 2017-2023
 Source: author's work based on Global Economy (2021) and State Statistics Service of Ukraine (2024b).

Data collection and correlation analysis of indices of national security threats in Ukraine and its GDP for the periods of 2017-2020 and 2017-2023 revealed opposite trends (Figure 5). If there was a strong inverse relationship between them before the war, as evidenced by a correlation coefficient of -0.98, then against the backdrop of the war, this dependence became a direct relationship (correlation coefficient of 0.85).

Efficient management of natural resource potential is achieved through program-targeted and project structures. Program-targeted structures for managing natural resources should focus on initiating and implementing local and national comprehensive programs by the state and business sector to enhance the effectiveness of environmental activities. This requires constant monitoring of the balance between production and consumption of natural resources and their impact on economic growth dynamics. As natural resources constitute the foundation of natural capital and the wealth of the economy, their value needs to be increased to meet the needs of local markets and exports. A necessary element of such management programs is the establishment of a proper institutional framework for identifying property rights over resources among stakeholders to mitigate conflicts over resources and resource rent. Management of natural resources should be based on principles of legality, decentralisation, and a differentiated approach to effectively utilise all available natural resource assets, particularly those that confer competitive advantages in international markets. Project management structure for natural resource assets is effective when implementing large-scale economic development strategies based on integrating diverse projects to achieve high-quality results. Therefore, management of natural resource potential serves as a system of effective managerial decisions for intensifying economic growth and enhancing resource security as a priority of national security. At the core of such a management system lie property relations over natural resources and their rent, processes of capitalisation of natural resources, and their rational utilisation. The superstructure of the management system involves implementing organisational mechanisms for the effective incorporation of program-targeted and project structures: legal, financial, and informational, to ensure high management performance, considering the scale of natural resource assets and threats to sustainable development and national security.

Figure 6. Conceptual model of effective natural resource management for intensifying economic growth and strengthening national security

The regulatory mechanism should encompass legislative acts and incentives within national and regional programs that can influence the growth and profitability of funding for environmental activities and natural resource management. These legislative acts should be harmonised with international documents and aligned with industry norms and standards to minimise environmental risks and threats. Such alignment will increase trust among stakeholders, including extractive companies, energy and resource consumers, investors, regulatory bodies, etc., in the strategy for managing natural resource potential.

To intensify economic growth and enhance national security, the primary priority of managing natural resource potential should be directing financial flows towards conserving natural resources and resource-efficient sustainable development. This is achieved through mechanisms investing in energy efficiency and conservation, renewable energy sources, strategic extraction of vital minerals, and environmentally clean production technologies.

Figure 6 illustrates the interdependencies of key trends in ensuring effective management of natural resource potential to accelerate economic growth and strengthen national security.

Informational and analytical support for the implementation of effective management strategies can significantly enhance the efficiency of natural resource management and amplify its positive impact on economic development and national security. The informational mechanism should include tools such as analytical systems for natural resource management and environmental protection, automation of document management systems, software products, and databases of resource-economic activities, as well as economic and environmental statistics. A special place in the operation of the informational mechanism, in our opinion, is occupied by resource-information systems, particularly powerful technologies such as geographic information systems (GIS) for analysing and monitoring natural resources, and for creating predictive models of the impact of resource potential on economic development. This includes remote sensing and satellite navigation systems, which provide reliable and timely information for managing natural resources, protecting the environment, and supporting sustainable development.

Discussion

This research was conducted within the framework of a conceptual approach, which views natural resource potential as the foundation of development and security for human civilization (Islam & Managi, 2019), a factor in economic growth (Song et al., 2020), an enhancer of quality of life (Bansal et al., 2021; Chopra et al., 2022), and a driver of transformational changes across all spheres of national security (Olanrewaju et al., 2020). Accordingly, we view the management of natural resources as a defence against threats associated with their irrational and environmentally harmful use (Wang et al., 2022), the escalation of conflicts over these resources and their rents (Alao, 2007; Joshua & Olanrewaju, 2017; Olanrewaju et al., 2020), as the foundational link in national security and economic growth. The scale of natural resource potential and its sufficiency for economic growth needs is not solely determined by its size, but rather by effective management of such potential and its proper institutionalisation. However, in economic literature, alternative approaches have emerged, suggesting that factors other than effective management of natural resource potential may be the leading drivers in transforming it into a reservoir of economic growth. It refers to the export orientation and reliance on external trade (Qiang & Jian, 2020), the potential of countries to reduce their own dependency on resources and flexibly reconfigure and diversify supply chains (Vekasi, 2021; Beal, 2022), as well as the development of a circular economy and improvement in resource utilization efficiency (Kumar et al., 2021), balancing investments in the economy and national security (Bauerle Danzman & Couloubaritsis, 2023).

We acknowledge that protection from threats to natural resource potential can be ensured by an effective natural resource management system, continuous monitoring of the use of natural resource assets, identification of property rights to them (Lei, 2020), and their capitalisation (Fan et al., 2020). According to our approach, only the factor of effective natural resource management will determine the trend of sustainable interdependence between economic growth, innovation shifts, and national security. This approach correlates with the approach of Qiang and Jian (2020) regarding the country's security dependence on its proper institutional framework and the disruptions of sectoral

imbalances in the economy due to unstable natural resource supplies and market turbulence. We agree with the thesis about the necessity of maintaining a balance between the use of resource assets and the needs of the economy to ensure growth (Hassan et al., 2019; Lampert, 2019; Altinoz & Dogan, 2021), and the depletion of natural resources hinders energy-efficient, sustainable development (Ramzan et al., 2022; Shahzad et al., 2022). The results of our study have demonstrated a strong positive correlation between resource rent and economic growth and the absence of a correlation between resource rent and the level of national security threats, contrary to the approach of Trung (2021), who suggests that a country's security depends on a certain level of resource utilisation and resource rent.

The same approach claims that states that depend on natural resources (victims of the "resource curse") use the proceeds from their sale to appease opposition groups and "pay off" the international community, thereby contributing to the political stability of the government (Trung, 2021). Based on the results of the current study, although it is not possible to confirm or refute Trung's conclusion, total dependence on natural resources is a sign of poor resource management and a low level of institutional development, which indicates a high level of threat to the national security of such states. The author also agreed that economic growth and natural resources improve financial development, while geopolitical risk worsens financial development, and the "resource curse" increases geopolitical risks (Qianqian et al., 2024). This indicates a direct connection between the "resource curse" and low national security, which was also mentioned by Trung.

Thus, the author's paper raises the issue of reassessing the importance of resource rents in the context of national security threats and opens the way for further research on the impact of other types of rents (financial and corruption) on national security. The policy implication should be to stop performing uncharacteristic economic functions for special services that provide protection against threats to national security. Thus, governments should decrease regulation of resource rents, leaving them to private agents, and concentrate on controlling the management of natural resources.

The strong suit of the current study is the strict adherence to the framework of the chosen conceptual approach. This may reveal some distortion of the results when trying to apply alternative approaches, although, as shown earlier, there was also a correlation of results when using a different approach.

Conclusions

The analysis found no correlation between the extraction of oil, coal, and gold and economic growth across countries, as indicated by a correlation coefficient of zero. Thus, the first hypothesis was rejected. A weak positive correlation (correlation coefficient of 0.35) between the level of threats to national security of countries and their economic growth was found, instead of a negative one. It indicated that the second hypothesis was also rejected.

A low positive correlation (correlation coefficient of 0.3) between the quality of governance of natural resource potential in the oil, gas, and mining sectors of different countries and their GDP growth was observed. On the other hand, a strong positive correlation was observed between the share of resource rent in the GDP of the studied countries and their economic growth. At the same time, a practical absence of a connection was found between the share of resource rent in the GDP of world countries and the level of threats to their national security.

An interesting trend was observed in the relationship between economic growth and national security threats in Ukraine. During the pre-invasion period (2017–2020), there was a strong negative correlation ($r = -0.98$), indicating that increased threats were associated with lower GDP growth. However, the correlation became strongly positive ($r = 0.85$) in the period 2020–2023; other factors, which were related to international economic and military-technical assistance, positively influenced GDP despite ongoing security threats. Thus, the third hypothesis held true only for the pre-war period and was rejected for 2020–2023.

Further research is required to identify additional factors influencing security threats and economic growth in Ukraine and to assess their specific impacts. A promising direction is to examine how the production and consumption of key natural resources affect these variables across a broader set of countries. Researchers interested in extending this study may also consider applying alternative conceptual frameworks for natural resource management. Comparing these with the current

findings could lead to the development of a synthesised approach that more accurately captures the factors driving effective resource governance. Based on the study of patterns in the relationship between economic growth and indicators of production, consumption of natural resources, the level of security threats, the quality of resource management and resource rent, the key principles of effective management of natural resource potential are identified, and the corresponding model is conceptualised.

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